

Analysis of MR Images for Early and Accurate Detection of Brain Tumor using Resource Efficient Simulator Brain Analysis ^{*}

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Abstract. Early detection of brain tumors is particularly important, as brain tumors are one of the leading causes of cancer-related mortality. However, identifying brain tumors can be challenging due to differences in tumor tissue variation among patients and, in some cases, the similarity of tumors to normal tissue. In this article, we propose a novel, resource-efficient simulator called Brain Analysis for fast and accurate analysis and verification of brain tumors. The proposed simulator aims to improve the reliability and speed of this process in treatment. To evaluate its performance, accuracy, and other important factors, we compare the proposed algorithm with several other methods, including a genetic algorithm, a CNN-based multi-classification model, an ML scheme + SVM approach, and a CapsNets model based on collective intelligence. Our experimental results show that the proposed algorithm significantly reduces the time needed to accurately detect early brain tumors, compared to the other methods, by using a multi-core architecture and appropriate filters in the Brain Analysis Simulator. This research objective demonstrates the potential of the proposed simulator as a component of a strategy for the early and faster detection of brain tumors.

Keywords: Brain Tumor · Brain Simulator · Multi-Core Architectures · Resource Efficient Simulators.

1 Introduction

Cancerous and CNS brain tumors rank tenth on the list of leading causes of death in humans, with more than 190,000 people diagnosed every year [1, 2]. However, early detection of brain tumors can reduce the risk of mortality. However, the causes of tumors are still uncertain, and any human being, whether a male, female, or child, may be stricken. Therefore, the initially identified tumor region could be a cause of the reduction in mortality risk. As a result, biologists and engineers are working together in the study of brain tumors using imaging approaches with the help of machine learning techniques [3]. The correct

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treatment of brain tumors includes several factors, such as the type and growth grade [4]. A brain tumor (BT) is further divided into two main classes, cancerous and noncancerous tumors category. Brain MRI or MR-image segmentation methods can be sub-categorized into three main classes: statistical-based and probabilistic, deformable model-based, and atlas-based approaches. In the literature different approaches have been presented that employed ML methodology, such as a k-nearest neighbor or KNN [5], support vector machines or SVM [6], decision trees, and artificial neural networks or ANNs, and principal component analysis or PCA [7]. However, these defined algorithms are used to work on features like hand-crafted, while training processes are required for mean feature extraction. Thus, the accuracy of the algorithm detection and classification only depends on the characteristics of the features. In [8], an effective segmenting strategy was explained using the k-means clustering technique integrated and compared with the Fuzzy C-means or FCM algorithm. The results of the integrated approach show that this novel approach improved K-means clustering algorithm performance, where FCM helps the combined algorithm to increase accuracy.

Our proposed architecture is a novel tool that offers fully automated, user-independent analysis and simulation results, including state-of-the-art accuracy and accurate tumor region segmentation of imbalanced MR images. In the proposed architecture, we used the following steps: first, various preprocessing algorithms (data cleaning, dimensionality reduction, feature engineering, imbalanced data, and data quality assessment) are applied to raw MR images to remove noise and other artifacts. Then, the watershed segmentation approach is used to segment the initial tumor region, and various features are extracted and analyzed from this segmented region. Finally, an SVM approach is applied to the resulting features for automated tumor classification. Overall, Brain Analysis represents a valuable tool in the field of medical image analysis and early brain tumor detection. Moreover, its open-source nature and run-time functionality make it a stand-alone simulator, and to the best of our knowledge, no other simulator offers these benefits. By making the simulator freely available for use by researchers, students, and medical professionals, the open-source characteristic opens up a wide range of possibilities for collaboration and integration with existing workflows. Furthermore, we believe it can be utilized as an interactive tool for workshops and training sessions to help bridge the gap between research and practical application [9]. Therefore, the Brain Analysis simulator opens up wide possibilities for collaboration and integration into existing workflows, making it a valuable tool for researchers and medical professionals.

2 Proposed Architecture

The proposed architecture used the Brain Tumor BraTS dataset [10]. The training dataset comprises 76 LGG (low-grade gliomas) and 259 HGG (high-grade gliomas) with 4 modalities (T1, T1c, T2, and T2FLAIR). For all experimental results, we used our proposed Brain Analysis Simulator. The proposed method

includes pre-processing steps, such as image quality enhancement and noise reduction, to improve the performance of segmentation and classification processing. The imbalanced input is converted into a grayscale image and optimized using a Gaussian filter for signal-to-noise ratio enhancement. The Gaussian filter is effective due to its image fading and brightening techniques, while the median filter can also be used to identify standard final pixel values.

The first part, pre-processing is important to prepare the image for the next processing steps, segmentation, and classification. Therefore, pre-processing is an essential method to eliminate the extra marks in the image [11]. The pre-processing method helps with further execution, image quality enhancement, and noise removal or reduction in the image which can increase performance in the segmentation and classification processing. Thus the solution presented herein, imbalanced input was converted into the gray-scale image and optimized the signal-to-noise ratio by using a Gaussian filter. The use of the Gaussian filtered algorithm in the proposed architecture is due to, its image fading and brightening techniques in which neighboring pixels contribute and participate in the operation to produce better and high-quality output [12], however, the use of the median filter is also performed for this purpose, as this filtration process identifies the standard final pixel values into the kernel. Therefore, Algorithm 1, describes the pre-processing implementation methodology,

Algorithm 1 Pre-processing Methodology

Input: imbalanced MRI images

Output: filtered images

Initialisation:

- 1: First statement
Image cropping
 - 2: Second statement
converting into grayscale images
 - 3: Third statement
Noise removal by using low pass filter
 - 4: Fourth statement
histogram adjustment
 - 5: Fifth statement
Binary format
 - 6: **if** (*pixel* \neq 0) **then**
 - 7: count value as a black pixel input
 - 8: **else**
 - 9: count value as a white pixel input
 - 10: **end if**
- END**
-

Additionally, Segmentation localizes the tumor area, and classification is the process to identify the type of tumor. Then, visualization gives the easy-to-understand outcome of the processing, results are presented in an easy-to-

understand format. For Segmentation, the architecture uses a combination of image segmentation methods, such as the watershed-based clustering and marker-based watershed approach, to segment the input image and identify the tumor area. This approach is widely used due to its robustness, precision, and efficiency. The use of a marker-based approach helps to resolve any over-segmentation issues that might occur during the segmentation process, as it is a region-growing methodology, which labels the regions for sure non-object or background and lasts the unknown region marked as 0. After segmentation, the feature extraction process is required for the binary classification, and for the classifier, we need these features for training. Feature extraction is a dimensionality reduction process part, this is a method for recognizing the shape and position of a tumor using the edge detection function in MRI-based images. In this proposed approach, we used the Grey-level co-occurrence matrix (GLCM) approach for extracting features for the classification of brain tumors. The GLCM function is a well-known approach for characterizing the image texture by memorizing the appearance of the paired pixel with specific values and in a specified structure relationship that occurs in an image, that creates a GLCM-Matrix. The visualization component provides a comprehensive view of the location and type of tumor, making it easy for medical practitioners and researchers to interpret and understand the results.

2.1 Availability

All experiments were conducted using a Brain Analysis Simulator. It is an open-source simulator that is publicly available for download with the user manual at <https://github.com/Rao-Sanaullah/Brain-Analysis-Simulator>.

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